

EFFECT OF DELAMINATIONS ON AN ELASTICALLY TAILORED LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATE

Jian Li* and Erian A. Armanios**
*School of Textile and Fiber Engineering
**School of Aerospace Engineering
Georgia Institute of Technology
Atlanta, Georgia 30332

ABSTRACT

A closed form solution is developed to analyze the influence of free-edge delaminations on an elastically tailored composite plate. The analysis is based on a shear deformation theory and a sublaminar approach. The solution is applied to predict the influence of free-edge delamination on the behavior of a class of laminates exhibiting extension-twist coupling.

1 INTRODUCTION

The potential application of unsymmetrical composite laminates has been brought into attention through the use of elastic tailoring which had its first application in aerospace industry. The advancement in the manufacturing processes also made possible the production of unsymmetrical laminates with tailored properties. However, the use of unsymmetrical laminates in structural design depends on the full understanding of their behavior under various loading conditions and their damage tolerance characteristics.

Composite laminates exhibit large interlaminar stresses at interfaces near the laminate free edges. It is well documented that delamination caused by interlaminar stresses arise at the free edges of symmetric laminate under uniform extension. Symmetric laminates subjected to other loading conditions also received some attention. However, limited work has been devoted to unsymmetrical laminates. Li [1], Armanios and Li [2] developed a simple analytical model to predict the interlaminar stresses and the total strain energy release rate for delaminated unsymmetrical laminates under extension. While symmetric configurations are simple to analyze and possess unique design and manufacturing advantages, their damage modes often alter their initial symmetry. An example is the case of a laminate subjected to unsymmetrical loading such as bending. Free edge delamination is expected to initiate on one side of the symmetry plane creating an unsymmetrical effect. Understanding and predicting the influence of free-edge delamination on the overall behavior of the laminates will provide quantitative measures of the extend of the damage to ensure their damaged tolerance.

2 ANALYTICAL MODEL

The laminate is assumed to be initially flat. Unsymmetrical lay-ups induce warping, bending or twisting as a result of residual curing stresses. Appropriate changes in design can lead to hygrothermally stable laminates. Such a design strategy is outlined in Winckler [3] in order to produce a family of unsymmetrical laminates that do not produce changes in curvature with changes in temperature or moisture content.

In Figure 1 a laminate is considered as made of sublaminates or groups of plies. Each sublaminar is treated as a homogeneous anisotropic body bounded by a cylindrical surface and

Figure 1: Sublaminates Notation and Sign Convention

subjected to interfacial stresses and end conditions. For a homogeneous anisotropic elastic body bounded by a cylindrical surface, a generalized plane deformation [4] exists when the stress tensor does not vary along the generator, x . The displacement field can be assumed as

$$u(x, y, z) = \epsilon_0 x + \kappa x(z + \delta) + U(y) + z\beta_x(y) \quad (1)$$

$$v(x, y, z) = V(y) + z\beta_y(y) + Cx(z + \delta) \quad (2)$$

$$w(x, y, z) = -\frac{1}{2}\kappa x^2 - Cx(y + \rho) + W(y). \quad (3)$$

where u , v , and w denote displacements relative to the x , y , and z axes, respectively. Axial extension is denoted by ϵ_0 , while κ is the bending curvature in the x - z plane. The relative angle of rotation about the x -axis, or twist, is denoted by C . The arbitrary constants δ and ρ are to be determined from continuity of displacements between sublaminates and from the overall boundary conditions. Shear deformation is recognized through the rotations β_x and β_y .

The corresponding strains are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \epsilon_{xx} &= \epsilon_{xx}^o + z\kappa_x & \epsilon_{yy} &= \epsilon_{yy}^o + z\kappa_y & \epsilon_{zz} &= 0 \\ \gamma_{xy} &= \gamma_{xy}^o + z\kappa_{xy} & \gamma_{yz} &= \gamma_{yz}^o & \gamma_{xz} &= \gamma_{xz}^o \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

The strain components associated with the reference surface are denoted by superscript o . These are defined as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \epsilon_{xx}^o &= \epsilon_0 + \kappa\delta & \epsilon_{yy}^o &= V_{,y} & \gamma_{xy}^o &= U_{,y} + C\delta \\ \kappa_x &= \kappa & \kappa_y &= \beta_{y,y} & \kappa_{xy} &= \beta_{x,y} + C \\ \gamma_{yz}^o &= \beta_y + W_{,y} & \gamma_{zx}^o &= \beta_x - C(y + \rho) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

where partial differentiation is denoted by a comma.

The constitutive relationship can be written in terms of resultant forces and moments and associated strains and curvatures as follows

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx}^o \\ \epsilon_{yy}^o \\ \gamma_{xy}^o \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} Q_y \\ Q_x \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{44} & A_{45} \\ A_{45} & A_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{yz}^o \\ \gamma_{xz}^o \end{Bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

For a sublaminates of thickness h , the stiffness coefficients in Equation 6 and Equation 7 are defined as

Figure 2: Delaminated Unsymmetrical Laminate Under Extension

$$(A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}) = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \bar{Q}_{ij}(1, z, z^2) dz \quad (8)$$

where the transformed reduced stiffnesses \bar{Q}_{ij} are defined similar to Vinson and Sierakowski [5]. The sublaminates equilibrium equations are obtained from the virtual work principle as

$$N_{xy,y} + t_{ux} - t_{lx} = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$N_{y,y} + t_{uy} - t_{ly} = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$Q_{y,y} + p_u - p_l = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$M_{xy,y} - Q_x + \frac{h}{2}(t_{ux} + t_{lx}) = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$M_{y,y} - Q_y + \frac{h}{2}(t_{uy} + t_{ly}) = 0 \quad (13)$$

where the interlaminar shear and peel stresses at the sublaminates upper and lower surfaces are denoted by t_{ux} , t_{uy} , p_u and t_{lx} , t_{ly} , p_l , respectively, as shown in Figure 1

At the sublaminates boundaries, $y=\text{constant}$, the following should be specified

$$N_{xy} \text{ or } U, N_y \text{ or } V, Q_y \text{ or } W, M_{xy} \text{ or } \beta_x, \text{ and } M_y \text{ or } \beta_y \quad (14)$$

3 ANALYSIS

For a symmetric laminate under anti-symmetric loading such as bending or torsion, or an unsymmetrical laminate under extension, free edge delaminations may develop in the upper or lower half of the laminate as shown in Figure 2. One half of the laminate cross section can be modeled using four sublaminates as shown in Figure 3. Also appearing in Figure 3 is the sublaminates numbering scheme and the coordinate systems. Sublaminates 2 and 3 represent the group of plies above and below the delamination, respectively, while sublaminates 1 and 0 represent the same group of plies in the uncracked portion.

The governing Equations 1 - 14 developed in the previous section will be applied to each sublaminates.

3.1 Kinematic Relations

To suppress the rigid body modes, it is assumed that the center of the laminate is fixed. That is, at $X=Y=Z=0$, we have

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u = v = w = 0 \\ v_{,X} = w_{,X} = v_{,Z} - w_{,Y} = 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (15)$$

Figure 3: Sublaminates Model and Coordinate Systems

The continuity of displacements at the interface between the sublaminates 1 and 0 can be written as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_0 \left(x, y, \frac{h_0}{2} \right) &= u_1 \left(x, y, -\frac{h_1}{2} \right) \\ v_0 \left(x, y, \frac{h_0}{2} \right) &= v_1 \left(x, y, -\frac{h_1}{2} \right) \\ w_0 \left(x, y, \frac{h_0}{2} \right) &= w_1 \left(x, y, -\frac{h_1}{2} \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (16)$$

where h_1 and h_0 denote the thicknesses of sublaminates 1 and 0, respectively.

Substituting Equations 1 through 3 into Equation 16, we have

$$\left. \begin{aligned} V_0 &= V_1 - \frac{h_1}{2} \beta_{y1} - \frac{h_0}{2} \beta_{y0} \\ U_0 &= U_1 - \frac{h_1}{2} \beta_{x1} - \frac{h_0}{2} \beta_{x0} \\ W_0 &= W_1 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (17)$$

From the displacement continuity conditions between sublaminates and the overall conditions in Equation 15, the constants δ and ρ for each sublaminates can be determined as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \delta_1 &= \delta_2 = \frac{h_0}{2} \\ \delta_0 &= \delta_3 = -\frac{h_1}{2} \\ \rho_0 &= \rho_1 = a - b \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (18)$$

3.2 Equilibrium Equations

The responses associated with sublaminates 0 and 1 are coupled through the interface continuity conditions in Equation 17. The upper surface of sublaminates 1 and the bottom surface of sublaminates 0 are stress free. The shear and peel stresses at the interface will be denoted by t_x , t_y , and p , respectively. Apply the equilibrium Equations 9 - 13 to sublaminates 0 and 1 to get

$$N_{xy1} + N_{xy0} = 0 \quad (19)$$

$$N_{y1} + N_{y0} = 0 \quad (20)$$

$$Q_{y1} + Q_{y0} = 0 \quad (21)$$

$$M_{xy1,y} + \frac{h_1}{2} N_{xy1,y} - Q_{x1} = 0 \quad (22)$$

$$M_{xy0,y} - \frac{h_0}{2} N_{xy0,y} - Q_{x0} = 0 \quad (23)$$

$$M_{y1,y} + \frac{h_1}{2} N_{y1,y} - Q_{y1} = 0 \quad (24)$$

$$M_{y0,y} - \frac{h_0}{2} N_{y0,y} - Q_{y0} = 0 \quad (25)$$

For sublaminates 2, the upper and lower surfaces are stress free. The equilibrium equations reduce to

$$N_{y2} = N_{xy2} = M_{y2} = Q_{y2} = 0 \quad (26)$$

$$M_{xy2,y} - Q_{x2} = 0 \quad (27)$$

Similarly, the equilibrium equations for sublaminates 3 can be written as

$$N_{y3} = N_{xy3} = M_{y3} = Q_{y3} = 0 \quad (28)$$

$$M_{xy3,y} - Q_{x3} = 0 \quad (29)$$

3.3 Boundary Conditions

The continuity conditions between sublaminates 1 and 2, and 0 and 3, and the boundary conditions at the free ends of sublaminates 2 and 3 can be written as

$$N_{y1}|_{y_1=0} = 0 \quad (30)$$

$$N_{xy1}|_{y_1=0} = 0 \quad (31)$$

$$M_{y1}|_{y_1=0} = 0 \quad (32)$$

$$M_{y0}|_{y_1=0} = 0 \quad (33)$$

$$M_{xy1}|_{y_1=0} = M_{xy2}|_{y_1=0} \quad (34)$$

$$M_{xy2}|_{y_1=-a} = 0 \quad (35)$$

$$M_{xy0}|_{y_0=0} = M_{xy3}|_{y_0=0} \quad (36)$$

$$M_{xy3}|_{y_0=-a} = 0 \quad (37)$$

3.4 Solution for the Rotations

The unknown functions U_1 , V_1 and W_1 can be expressed in terms of the rotations of sublaminates 0 and 1 using Equations 19- 21. Consequently, Equation 22 through Equation 25 can be reduced to four ordinary differential equations in terms of the rotations of sublaminates 1 and 0. The integration constants can be obtained from Equation 30 through Equation 33. The rotations β_{2x} and β_{3x} are obtained similarly.

3.5 Loading Conditions

The laminate is assumed to be subjected to an extension force F_X , bending moment M_B and twisting moment M_T at its ends. These are expressed in terms of the sublaminates forces and moments by

$$F_X = 2 \int_0^{b-a} (N_{x1} + N_{x0})dy + 2 \int_{-a}^0 (N_{x2} + N_{x3})dy \quad (38)$$

$$M_B = 2 \int_0^{b-a} (M_{x1} + M_{x0} + \delta_1 N_{x1} + \delta_0 N_{x0})dy + 2 \int_{-a}^0 (M_{x2} + M_{x3} + \delta_1 N_{x2} + \delta_0 N_{x3})dy \quad (39)$$

$$M_T = 4 \int_0^{b-a} [M_{xy1} + M_{xy0} + \delta_1 N_{xy1} + \delta_0 N_{xy0}]dy + 4 \int_{-a}^0 [M_{xy2} + M_{xy3}]dy \quad (40)$$

The force and moment resultants in Equations 38, 39 and 40 can be written in terms of extensional strain, bending curvature and twist as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} F_X \\ M_B \\ M_T \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{11} & \alpha_{12} & \alpha_{13} \\ \alpha_{21} & \alpha_{22} & \alpha_{23} \\ \alpha_{31} & \alpha_{32} & \alpha_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_0 \\ \kappa \\ C \end{Bmatrix} \quad (41)$$

Matrix $[\alpha]$ represents the stiffness of the delaminated laminate. Its elements α_{ij} are in general unsymmetric and are determined from

$$[\alpha] = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 (F_{11}^i + \bar{F}_{11}^i) & 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 (F_{12}^i + \bar{F}_{12}^i) & 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 (F_{13}^i + \bar{F}_{13}^i) \\ 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 (F_{41}^i + \bar{F}_{21}^i) & 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 (F_{42}^i + \bar{F}_{22}^i) & 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 (F_{43}^i + \bar{F}_{23}^i) \\ 4 \sum_{i=0}^1 F_{61}^i + \bar{F}_{31}^i & 4 \sum_{i=0}^1 F_{62}^i + \bar{F}_{32}^i & 4 \sum_{i=0}^1 F_{63}^i + \bar{F}_{33}^i \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 \delta_i (F_{11}^i + \bar{F}_{11}^i) & 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 \delta_i (F_{12}^i + \bar{F}_{12}^i) & 2 \sum_{i=0}^1 \delta_i (F_{13}^i + \bar{F}_{13}^i) \\ 4 \sum_{i=0}^1 \delta_i F_{31}^i & 4 \sum_{i=0}^1 \delta_i F_{32}^i & 4 \sum_{i=0}^1 \delta_i F_{33}^i \end{bmatrix} \quad (42)$$

The parameters in Equation 42 are elements from the following matrices

$$[F^1] = \langle [\gamma^1] + [\xi^1] \{\bar{q}\} (0 \ 0 \ 1) \rangle (b-a) - [\xi^1] [\Phi] [\zeta] [\bar{G}] \quad (43)$$

$$[F^0] = \langle [\gamma^0] + [\xi^0] \{\bar{q}\} (0 \ 0 \ 1) \rangle (b-a) - [\xi^0] [\Phi] [\zeta] [\bar{G}] \quad (44)$$

$$[\bar{F}^1] = [\bar{\gamma}^1] a + \{\bar{\xi}^1\} (\omega^c) [H] \quad (45)$$

$$[\bar{F}^0] = [\bar{\gamma}^0] a + \{\bar{\xi}^0\} (\omega^d) [I] \quad (46)$$

where $[\zeta]$ is a diagonal matrix whose elements are defined as

$$\zeta_{ii} = 1 \quad \text{for } s_i = 0 \quad (47)$$

$$\zeta_{ii} = a - b \quad \text{for } s_i \neq 0 \quad (48)$$

and

$$(\omega^c) = \{ \sinh(s_c a) \quad 1 - \cosh(s_c a) \quad a \} \quad (49)$$

$$(\omega^d) = \{ \sinh(s_d a) \quad 1 - \cosh(s_d a) \quad a \} \quad (50)$$

Explicit expressions for matrices $[\gamma^1]$, $[\xi^1]$, $[\gamma^0]$, $[\xi^0]$, $[\bar{\gamma}^1]$, $[\bar{\xi}^1]$, $[\bar{\gamma}^0]$, $[\bar{\xi}^0]$, $[\Phi]$, $[\bar{G}]$, $[H]$, $[I]$ and vector $\{\bar{q}\}$ are provided in Reference [1]. For a laminate subjected to an extension force F_X only, the induced bending curvature κ and twist C can be obtained as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \kappa \\ C \end{Bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{22} & \alpha_{23} \\ \alpha_{32} & \alpha_{33} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha_{21} \\ \alpha_{31} \end{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_0 \quad (51)$$

The induced bending curvature and twist are functions of the delamination length, a . The ratio of twice the twist over the extension force, defined as the extension-twist coupling parameter and denoted by β_{16d} , is written as

$$\beta_{16d} = \frac{2C}{F_X/2b} \quad (52)$$

Similarly, the induced curvature and extensional strain can be obtained for a laminate subjected to a bending moment M_B , and for a laminate subjected to a twist moment M_T .

4 APPLICATION

The solution developed in Section 3 will be used to analyze a class of unsymmetrical laminates with $[-\theta, (90 - \theta)_2, -\theta, \theta, (\theta - 90)_2, \theta]_T$ lay-up. This class of laminates is designed to exhibit extension-twist coupling with no initial warping due to curing stress.

The laminate geometry and material properties are given in Table 1. It is seen from Equation 51 that the induced twist and bending curvature are expressed in terms of the stiffness, α_{ij} , which is dependent on the delamination length and its location in the laminate.

Table 1: Geometry and Material Properties of AS4-3502 Graphite/Epoxy

$E_{11}=113.31$ GPa
$E_{22}=E_{33}=9.73$ GPa
$G_{12}=G_{13}=5.66$ GPa
$G_{23}=3.40$ GPa
$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}=0.25$
$\nu_{23}=0.42$
Ply thickness $H=0.14$ mm
Semi-width $b=68H$.

Figure 4: Influence of Free-Edge Delamination on Extension-Twist Coupling for $\theta = 30^\circ$

The effect of free-edge delamination on the extension-twist coupling is isolated by considering the extension-twist coupling parameter, β_{16d} . Free-edge delamination is assumed at one interface at a time starting from the bottom interface or interface 1 between θ and $(\theta - 90)$ up to the top interface or interface 7 between $(90 - \theta)$ and $-\theta$. Angles θ of 30° , 40° and 50° are considered. Parameter β_{16d} normalized by β_{16u} is shown in Figure 4 through 6. Where β_{16d} and β_{16u} denote the extension-twist coupling parameter for a laminate with and without free-edge delamination, respectively. An explicit expression for β_{16u} is given in Reference [1]. A delamination length of 15 ply thickness is assumed for all cases.

The influence of free-edge delamination on the extension-twist coupling depends on the interface location and the lay-up angle θ . For the case of $\theta = 30^\circ$, the extension-twist coupling decreases irrespective of the interface in which free-edge delamination occurs. For $\theta = 40^\circ$, the induced twist changes directions when the delamination is placed at interface 2 or 6. For $\theta = 50^\circ$,

Figure 5: Influence of Free-Edge Delamination on Extension-Twist Coupling for $\theta = 40^\circ$

Figure 6: Influence of Free-Edge Delamination on Extension-Twist Coupling for $\theta = 50^\circ$

the extension-twist coupling can increase by as much as 350%.

5 CONCLUSION

Free-edge delamination may decrease or increase extension-twist coupling depending on the location of the delamination and the lay-up of the laminate. This indicates that free edge delamination may be detected through the associated variation in coupling at low level of applied loads. Furthermore, the influence of delamination on the coupling should be considered in the design of elastically tailored composites in order to ensure their damage tolerance.

References

- [1] Li, J., Interlaminar Fracture Analysis of Laminated Composites Under Combined Loading, Ph.D. Thesis, School of Aerospace Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology, 1992, pp. 63-104.
- [2] Armanios, E. A. and Li, J., Interlaminar Fracture Analysis of Unsymmetrical Laminates, *Composite Materials: Fatigue and Fracture, Fourth Volume, ASTM STP 1156*, W. W. Stinchcomb and N. E. Ashbaugh, Eds., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1993, pp. 341-360.
- [3] Winckler, S. I., Hygrothermally Curvature Stable Laminates with Tension-Torsion Coupling, *Journal of the American Helicopter Society*, Vol. 31, No. 7, July 1985, pp. 56-58.
- [4] Lekhnitskii, S. G., *Theory of Elasticity of an Anisotropic Body*, Holden-Day, Inc., San Francisco, 1963, pp. 103-108.
- [5] Vinson, J. R. and Sierakowski, R. L., *The behavior of structures composed of composite materials*, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, 1986, pp. 46-47.